

ON THE PROBLEM OF LEARNING SOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7952289>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the topic of somatic phraseology in Uzbek linguistics. Somatic phrases, i.e. expressions related to human body parts, are studied in Uzbek linguistics.*

Keywords: *phraseology, idiom, phraseological unit, proverb, somatism, figurative expression, wise word.*

In the process of effective use of expressions in oral and written speech, thinking, imagination, memory and word, cognitive abilities are developed, as it provides an opportunity to deeply understand the expressed thought.

In the context of the Uzbek language, phraseologisms are now referred to by terms such as phraseological phrase, phraseological unit, phraseological combination. We cannot say that phraseology has been systematically and fully studied in Turkic studies, especially in Uzbek studies.

It should be noted that in Uzbek linguistics, methodical study of phraseologisms has also been established. Features of methodological use of phraseologisms in the works of Uzbek writers and poets are reflected in many candidate theses.

In particular, M.M. In her article, Rustamova examines the lexical connection of somatisms as a component in phraseological units in Italian and Uzbek languages, analyzes Italian phraseological units with somatisms and compares them with their alternatives in Uzbek. During the analysis, similarities are noted, and unique aspects are discussed separately.

Sh.R. Usmanova f.f. in the thesis submitted for the candidate's scientific degree, he considered somatic phraseology in Uzbek and Turkish languages.

In this work, somatic phraseologisms in the Uzbek and Turkish languages are comparatively studied in terms of lexical-semantic and grammatical construction. It is intended to solve the following issues:

- the amount of somatic phraseology in the Uzbek and Turkish languages, identifying the somas actively involved in their structure;
- structural-syntactic classification of somatic phraseology of Uzbek and Turkish languages;
- classification of somatic phraseology according to base terms and predicate character;
- by grouping phrases equal to the combination in both languages into alternative and incompatible phrases, identifying and summarizing the substantive and formal similarities and differences between them;
- clarifying specific semantic-syntactic features based on the grouping of phrases equivalent to a sentence in both languages into alternative and inappropriate phrases and dividing them into simple phrase phrases and compound phrase phrases according to their structure.

Somatic phraseology in the Uzbek language is studied in A. Isayev's candidate thesis entitled "Somatic phraseology of the Uzbek language". In this scientific work, the amount of somatic phraseology in the modern Uzbek literary language, their communicative functions,

variantness, synonymy, homonymy and antonymy are studied. Focusing in detail on phrases made with the word "head" and "eye", a comparative analysis of them with Tatar, Turkmen and Azerbaijani variants is given. The scientist restricts the range of somatic phraseology and opposes including the names of animal body parts. At the same time, he says that there is no reason to include words such as soul and heart in the somatic lexicon.

The main part of the phraseology of most languages in the world is somatic phraseologisms. Somatic phraseologisms are units that include somatisms, that is, words denoting the names of body parts. Centuries-old experience, lifestyle, culture, spirituality, customs and traditions of each nation are reflected in somatic phraseology.

In world linguistics, a number of scientific studies were conducted within the framework of somatic phraseologisms. One of the first researchers of somatic phraseology is F. Buck. He divided all somatic phraseology into three groups: expressions describing only people, describing people and animals, and expressing only animals. In the following years, somatic phraseologisms were comparatively studied within the framework of languages of different systems. In this place, significant progress was made in the research of scientists such as Y. Dolgoplov (somatic phraseology in Russian, English and German), M. Abilgaliyeva (somatic phraseology in Kazakh and German), D. Saipullayeva (somatic phraseology in Turkmen and English).

The semantics of somatic phraseologisms of Turkic languages was studied by D. Bazarova. The scientist showed the importance of somatic phraseologisms in the formation of not only lexical, but also grammatical categories.

In modern linguistics, many scientific works related to the study of phrasal units have been created. In these works, along with the lexical-semantic aspects of the expressions within a certain language (or several languages), the functional properties are also thoroughly researched. At the same time, the volume of works dedicated to the analysis of expressions involving somatisms is also significant.

Uzbek linguists have also carried out significant research on the principles of formation of phraseological units in the language, their living conditions in the functional forms of Uzbek speech, methodological possibilities, including their emotional and expressive functions in artistic and journalistic texts. These observations were made based on the comparison of not only one language, but also several languages. The research conducted by A. Isaev, O. Nazarov, Sh. Usmonova, Sh. Nazirova, H. Alimova on the study of somatic phraseologisms made an important contribution to the study of the linguistic and ontological nature of phraseological units in the Uzbek language. . Issues such as human and non-human factors in the formation of phraseologisms, the role of words in the decision-making in terms of expression and content, the aspects of spiritual formation, the lexical and semantic features of the formation of new phraseologisms based on existing universal phraseologisms with motivational and derivational bases of formation are covered in Mamatov's doctoral dissertation.

In particular, A. Isaev's candidate thesis entitled "Somatic phraseology in the Uzbek language" is of great importance in Uzbek linguistics. This dissertation, which was defended 42 years ago, focuses on the component analysis of somatic phrases in the Uzbek language and the identification of similarities and differences with related Turkic languages. In the table, it was concluded that the tongue (29 times), head (28), eye (27) and hand (22) are the most used somatisms in 41 phraseological expressions. However, marrow somatism was not included in this list. In the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" it is stated that the word "marrow"

means the fatty substance inside the bone. However, expressions such as "marrow is full", "marrow dry", "marrow burst", "marrow play" were formed on the basis of this lexical somatism.

The scientist studied about 1400 phrases with a somatic component, which made up 17.5% of the phraseological fund of the Uzbek language, based on the card file of more than 8000 phraseologisms collected by H. Berdiyurov.

However, in this study, phenomena such as structural changes and transformation of somatic phrases, and the stylistic and semantic-pragmatic possibilities they manifest in the text, have been neglected.

In conclusion, a number of scientific studies created in Uzbek linguistics play a major role in the formation and development of the phraseology of the Uzbek language. In particular, doctor's and candidate's theses dedicated to researching this or that problem of phraseologisms were defended. Dozens of monographs, scientific articles, training manuals, and phraseological dictionaries were created.

REFERENCES

1. Турсунов У., Мухторов Ж., Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ҳозирги ўзбек адабий тили. Тошкент шаҳри: Ўқитувчи, 1992.
2. Қўчқортойев И. бадий нутқ стилистикаси. - Тошкент, 1975.
3. Йўлдошев Б. Фразеологик услубият асослари. - Самарқанд.
4. Ғ.Ғулом. «Шум бола». Тошкент шаҳри. 1989-йил.
5. Ш. Раҳматуллаев Ўзбек тилининг фразеологик луғати. – Тошкент шаҳри, 1992.
6. Ш.Раҳматуллаев. Ҳозирги адабий ўзбек тили. –Тошкент шаҳри, 2006.
7. «Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати». «Ўзбекистон миллий энсклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, Тошкент шаҳри, 2006-2008-йиллар.